

(360 ml) and the stirring was continued for a further 2 h. After standing overnight the solution was acidified to congo red, filtered from a crystalline deposit and then extracted with benzene (100 ml). The solid and the concentrate of the benzene extract were the unchanged starting material (1.4 g). The aqueous layer was refluxed for 4 h with the addition of benzene (200 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml). The benzene layer was separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled off. The yellow crystalline mass obtained was crystallised from hot water to fine yellow needles (3.7 g, 33.3%), m.p. 115–17° (Found: C, 54.48; H, 5.91. $C_{11}H_{14}O_6$ requires: C, 54.54; H, 5.83%).

2-Hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (7): An ethereal solution of diazomethane generated from nitrosomethylurea (40.0 g) was dried over potassium hydroxide pellets. The methanolic solution of 2,5-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (10.0 g) was added to the ethereal solution of diazomethane. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The excess diazomethane and the solvent were then removed from reaction mixture under reduced pressure. The crude liquid product was distilled at 115°/2 mm (8.5 g, 80%) (Found: C, 56.18; H, 6.32. $C_{12}H_{16}O_6$ requires: C, 56.24; H, 6.29%).

2-(2',4',5'-Trimethoxybenzoyloxy)-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (8): 2,4,5-Trimethoxybenzoyl chloride (prepared from 2.3 g 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzoic acid) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (2.0 g) in dry pyridine (15 ml) and heated at 100° for 1 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice after the removal of pyridine under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The ester (8) was crystallised from acetone-ethanol as colourless needles (3.0 g, 85%), m.p. 180–81° (Found: C, 58.58; H, 6.01. $C_{22}H_{26}O_{10}$ requires: C, 58.66; H, 5.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1728 (ester C=O) and 1670 cm^{-1} ($COCH_3$).

2-Hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (9): Powdered potassium hydroxide (3.0 g) was added to a solution of the ester (8; 2.5 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) and heated at 60° with stirring for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified. The resulting yellow diketone was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from methanol as yellow needles (1.87 g, 75%), m.p. 129–30° (Found: C, 58.60; H, 5.91. $C_{22}H_{26}O_{10}$ requires: C, 58.66; H, 5.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300–3600 (OH), 1617 (chelated β -diketone), 1570 and 1525 cm^{-1} (aromatic); positive $FeCl_3$ test.

5,6,7,8,2',4',5'-Heptamethoxyflavone (Agecorynin-C) (3): A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (1.0 g), fused sodium acetate (1.8 g) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. Acetic acid was then removed under reduced pressure and water added to the cooled reaction mixture. The separated flavone was crystallised from acetone-pentane as colourless solid (0.76 g, 80%), m.p. 159–60° (lit.¹ 158–60°)

(Found: C, 59.89; H, 5.97. $C_{22}H_{24}O_9$ requires: C, 61.10; H, 5.59%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 (C=O), 1570 and 1520 cm^{-1} (aromatics); δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.95 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.97 (9H, s, $3 \times OCH_3$), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.57 (s, 3-H), 7.04 (s, 3'-H) and 7.54 (s, 6'-H).

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Studies on Vilsmeier-Haack Reaction. A New Route to 2-Chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehydes and a Furoquinoline Derivative†

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IN continuation of our interest in Vilsmeier-Haack reaction¹ and its synthetic applications, *para*-substituted-acetophenone oximes (**1a–d**) were converted into 2-chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehydes (**2a–d**) in one step by Vilsmeier-Haack reagent (DMF/ $POCl_3$). We made use of this versatile intermediate **2** to build a linear furoquinoline derivative by a simple route (Scheme 1).

2-Chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehyde is a versatile synthetic intermediate² because chlorine can be displaced by reactive nucleophiles and the aldehyde group is a suitable proximate reactive function for the construction of new heterocyclic ring. We report here a one-pot synthesis of compound **2**. Compounds **1a–d** were converted into **2a–d** using excess of $POCl_3$ (7 mol) and dimethylformamide (3 mol) by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction. Melting points and ir spectra of **2a–d** were found identical with those of the authentic samples prepared by the reported method².

The plausible mechanism for the reaction may involve Beckmann transformation of the oxime with aryl group migration to give acetanilides *in situ*

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Scheme 1

followed by (V.H.) formylation to furnish the product in one-step.

Intermediate **2** could be used to build up furoquinolines which are rather difficult to synthesise³. Hydrolysis of **2b** was carried out with 6N HCl to give 2-oxo-3-formyl-6-methylquinoline (**3**), which showed in its ir bands at 3 520, 3 400 (NH), 1 700 (H-C=O), 1 360 (C=O, amide-I), 1 540 (amide-II), 896 and 815 cm⁻¹. This on treatment with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of base gave the aryloxy ester (**4**). Identity of **4** was based on elemental analysis and ir bands at 1 725 (ester C=O), 1 250 (O=C-OEt), 1 700 (H-C=O) and 815 cm⁻¹ (*para*-disubstituted benzene ring). This was modified to furan ring system **5** by cyclisation with sodium acetate in acetic anhydride. The structure was given on the basis of microanalysis and ir bands⁴ at 1 483, 1 380, 1 172 and 1 121 cm⁻¹ (substituted furan ring), 1 600, and bands at 1 087 cm⁻¹ (C=C of furan ring), 1 750 (ester C=O), 1 250 (O=C-OEt) indicated the formation of the furoquinoline derivative (**5**).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were taken on Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer. *para*-Substituted-oximes were prepared according to literature⁵ procedures.

Vilsmeier-Haack reaction of para-substituted-acetophenone oximes: To dimethyl formamide (9.6 ml, 0.12 mol) cooled to 0°, freshly distilled phosphoryl chloride (32 ml, 0.35 mol) was added

dropwise under stirring. The oxime (**1**) was then added to it and the reaction mixture heated to 60° for 16 h. It was poured into ice-water (300 ml) and stirred for 30 minutes. The chloroquinoline-3-carboxyaldehyde (**2**) was filtered and crystallised from ethyl acetate: **2a** (57%), m.p. 145° (lit.² 145°); **2b** (51%), m.p. 124° (lit.² 129°); **2c** (10%), m.p. 172° (lit.² 171°); **2d** (13%), m.p. 146° (lit.² 146°).

2-Oxo-3-formyl-6-methylquinoline (3): 2-Chloroquinoline-6-methyl-3-carboxyaldehyde (**2b**; 4 g) was heated on a water-bath with concentrated HCl (20 ml) for 2 h. It was then poured into ice with constant stirring. The resulting yellow solid was crystallised from acetic acid, (70%), m.p. 145° (Found: N, 7.97. C₁₁H₉O₂N requires: N, 8.00%)

Ethyl 3-formyl-6-methyl-2-quinolinylloxy acetate (4): A mixture of **3** (2 g), ethyl chloroacetate (3 ml) and water (12 ml) was slowly added aqueous NaOH (1.2 g in 30 ml H₂O) and the mixture was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3 h. The hot solution was kept overnight. The yellow crystals were separated, (40%), m.p. 300° (Found: N, 2.51. C₁₅H₁₅O₄N requires: N, 2.33%).

Furoquinoline ester (5): A mixture of quinolinyl-oxy ester (**4**; 1 g), anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g), acetic acid (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was refluxed for 8 h and then poured into ice-water (100 ml), stirred and allowed to stand for a few hours with occasional stirring. The product was extracted with ether. On work-up a solid was obtained which was crystallised from methanol, (50%), m.p. 155° (Found: N, 5.41. C₁₅H₁₃O₃N requires: N, 5.49%).

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